

SUPPLEMENTARY ON-LINE MATERIAL

Satiety hormone LEAP2 after low-calorie diet with/without Endobarrier insertion in obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus

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SUPPLEMENTARY METHODS

2.2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria for Endobarrier study

Inclusion criteria for participants were diagnosis of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) for at least one year, age 18–65 years, male or female, HbA1c 7.7%–11.0% (equivalent to 58–97mmol/mol), on oral glucose lowering medications only, and body mass index (BMI) 30–50 kg/m².

Exclusion criteria included use of insulin or GLP-1 analogues at recruitment, previous bariatric surgery, history of anaemia, liver or kidney impairment, severe mental illness, current depression, and (for the fMRI subgroup only) current smokers and gluten or lactose intolerance, being vegan or vegetarian. For complete list see published protocol paper (Glaysher et al. 2017, Ruban et al. 2020).

All participants gave written informed consent, and the study was approved by the NHS Research Ethics Committee London - Fulham (REC 14/LO/0871) and conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

2.3. Blood collection, storage and assay

Fasting blood samples were taken at -2, 2, 26, 50 and 104 week visits, with post-prandial samples collected at the same visits excluding week 104. Plasma glucose, and serum insulin, triglycerides and HbA1c were assayed using routine clinical laboratory assays as reported previously (Glaysher et al. 2017, Ruban et al. 2020). Homeostasis model assessment of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR) was calculated using the formula: Fasting insulin (mU/L) x fasting glucose (mmol/L)/22.5 (Matthews et al. 1985). Blood was collected in lithium heparin tubes containing protease inhibitors aprotinin (Trasylol, Nordic Pharma Ltd., UK) and AEBSF (4-(2-aminoethyl)benzenesulfonyl fluoride hydrochloride) (A8456; Sigma-Aldrich, Dorset, UK), as previously described (Mani et al. 2019, Bhargava et al. 2023). Plasma samples were stored at -80°C for future measurement of gut hormones.

Plasma LEAP2 concentrations were measured using a commercial enzyme immunoassay (EK-075-40, Phoenix

Pharmaceuticals Inc., CA, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. This LEAP2 assay has been previously validated using human samples (Mani et al. 2019, Bhargava et al. 2023). Plasma samples were diluted 10 times in the assay buffer. The detectable assay range was 0-100 ng/mL, and inter-assay and intra-assay coefficients of variation were both within the manufacturer guidance at 14.9% and 4.6% respectively.

2.4. Sweet taste task adjustment

Data from weeks -2, 2 and 26 weeks from the taste sub-group were analysed using mixed-effects model to examine the effect of sweet taste task on absolute variables: fasting plasma LEAP2, HbA1c, plasma glucose, serum insulin, HOMA-IR, plasma triglycerides, and fasting VAS appetite ratings across all visits, as this task was performed prior to blood collection and VAS ratings in this taste mechanistic sub-group (Table S1). Analysis included group (SMM vs. DJBL) and sweet taste task (yes, no) as between participant factors, and weeks as a within participant factor. For dependent variables with an overall main effect of sweet taste task, or sweet taste task*weeks interaction, adjusted values were calculated using the mean effect size for -2, 2, 26 weeks to remove the effects of sweet taste task. Manually adjusted dependent variables were then used in correlational analysis if the variable was significantly affected by sweet taste task.

There were no significant sweet taste task*weeks interactions, but there were significant main effects of sweet taste task on fasting plasma LEAP2, plasma glucose, serum insulin and HOMA-IR (P=0.022 to <0.001) (Supplementary Tables Table S1, S2). The mean effect size of participating in the sweet taste task at individual visits for each group was calculated from post-hoc analysis and used to adjust fasting plasma LEAP2, plasma glucose, serum insulin, and HOMA-IR with adjusted values.

2.5. Statistical analysis

2.5.1. Longitudinal analysis of study outcomes

Anthropological measures: Demographic data is presented as mean \pm SEM or median [interquartile range, IQR] if not normally distributed. Data was checked for normal distribution using the Shapiro-Wilk test (Table 1). A mixed-effects model was performed on the medication participants took throughout the study duration

to examine significant changes within drug classes at each visit (-2, 2, 26, 50, 104 weeks). The drug classes investigated were: metformin, sulphonylureas (SU), sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 inhibitors (SGLT2i), dipeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors (DPP4i), glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP1RA), thiazolidinediones (TZD), insulin, meglitinide and beta adrenoreceptor antagonists (beta-blockers) (Supplementary Figure S8, Tables S3, S4).

Fasting analysis: Longitudinal data from the Endobarrier study were analysed using mixed-effects model to examine changes in dependent variables: absolute fasting plasma LEAP2, BMI, changes in: fasting plasma LEAP2, % weight, HbA1c, fasting plasma glucose, insulin, HOMA-IR, plasma triglycerides, and fasted VAS appetite, hunger and fullness ratings across all visits (vs. -2 week visit). Analysis included the following between-participant factors: participant ID, group (SMM vs. DJBL) and weeks as a within-participant factor. Post-hoc analyses using Fisher's LSD test to examine differences from baseline visit (-2 weeks) and between groups. This analysis was also run separately for each group to identify any within-group changes in fasting plasma LEAP2, BMI, % weight, HbA1c, fasting plasma glucose, HOMA-IR, plasma triglycerides, and fasted appetite, hunger and fullness VAS ratings. Sweet taste task was additionally included only for fasting plasma LEAP2, plasma glucose, insulin and HOMA-IR (Supplementary Tables S1, S2, Supplementary Methods 2.4).

Post-prandial analysis: Identical analyses were performed in the taste sub-group of the Endobarrier study for % weight change, post-prandial plasma LEAP2 iAUC0-120min, appetite iAUC0-120min, fullness iAUC0-120min, but without the sweet taste task correction. In the taste cohort, the incremental area under the curve (iAUC0-120min) was calculated using the trapezoid rule for post-prandial plasma LEAP2 and fed appetite VAS ratings, by subtracting fasting (t=0mins) from fed (t=+60 to +120mins after food intake) measures for each participant. Comparisons between time points (t=0,60 and 120mins) for increase in post-prandial plasma LEAP2 was made using a general linear model including time as within-participant factor, with post-hoc Fisher's LSD test at baseline visit (-2 weeks). Comparisons of post-prandial plasma LEAP2 response between visits (-2,2,26,50 weeks) within-group (SMM, DJBL) was performed using a mixed-effects model with post-hoc Fisher's LSD test.

2.5.2. Bivariate and correlational analysis of data

Fasted analysis: Bivariate analysis was conducted separately for the DJBL group from -2 to 50 weeks and SMM group from -2 to 104 weeks. The effect of the variable on the absolute and change from baseline visit (-2 weeks) of fasting plasma LEAP2 were analysed as the absolute and change from week -2 of variable: BMI, % weight, HbA1c, fasting plasma glucose, insulin, HOMA-IR, plasma triglycerides, and fasted VAS appetite and hunger ratings. Fasting plasma LEAP2, plasma glucose, insulin and HOMA-IR had values adjusted accordingly due to the sweet taste task. Bivariate analysis was conducted using a mixed-effects model to report r^2 value, slope (β) and P-value.

DJBL explant sub-group: For the DJBL group from weeks 50 to 104, after the explant of the DJBL device, the relationships between change from 50-104 weeks in plasma LEAP2 with change from 50-104 weeks in % weight, HbA1c, fasting plasma glucose, insulin, HOMA-IR, plasma triglycerides, and fasted VAS appetite and hunger ratings. Correlation analysis was performed to examine the relationships between outcome variables (without any covariates) in the DJBL group from 50-104 weeks, reporting Pearson's (r_p) if data was normally distributed, or Spearman's (r_s) correlation coefficients if either variable was not normally distributed and P-value.

Post-prandial analysis: Bivariate analysis was conducted separately for the DJBL group from -2 to 50 weeks and SMM group from -2 to 104 weeks. The effect of absolute and change from baseline visit (-2 week) of variable post-prandial plasma LEAP2 $iAUC_{0-120min}$ on the absolute and change from baseline visit (-2 week) of post-prandial appetite $iAUC_{0-120min}$, post-prandial hunger $iAUC_{0-120min}$ was investigated. Bivariate analysis was conducted using a mixed-effects model to report r^2 value, slope (β) and p-value. For correlations between post-prandial plasma LEAP2 and appetite, the difference in the incremental area under curve (iAUC) between 0 and 120 min ($iAUC_{0-120min}$) was calculated at -2, 2, 26 and 50 weeks, when the participants were given fixed test meals. Additional correlational analysis was performed across different studies using absolute difference in post-prandial (fed-fasted) plasma LEAP2 and meal size consumed in kilocalories.

All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS version 29 (Armonk, NY, USA) and GraphPad Prism v9.5.1 (San Diego, CA, USA) with effects considered significant at $P < 0.05$ and a trend at $P < 0.10$.

SUPPLEMENTARY RESULTS

3.2.2. Longitudinal changes in fasting glucose metabolism

SMM group

Over 104 weeks, there was a significant effect of weeks on *changes* in: HbA1c [F(4, 97.38)=21.60, P<0.001], HOMA-IR [F(4, 108.19)=6.34, P<0.001], fasting plasma glucose [F(4, 109.22) = 11.39, P<0.001] and fasting plasma insulin [F(4, 108.19)=4.45, P=0.003] (Figure 1C, D, E, Supplementary Table S5). In post-hoc analysis, HbA1c decreased the most from baseline at 26 weeks (effect size -16.56 ± 2.06 mol/mmol [95% CI -20.64, -12.46], P<0.001), remain below baseline at 104 weeks (effect size -6.89 ± 2.17 mol/mmol [95% CI -11.20, -2.59], P=0.002) (Figure 1C, Supplementary Table S6). HOMA-IR decreased the most from baseline at 26 weeks (effect size -2.19 ± 0.49 [95% CI -3.16, -1.21], P<0.001) (Figure 1E, Supplementary Table S6). Fasting plasma glucose decreased the most from baseline at 2 weeks (effect size -3.01 ± 0.47 mmol/L [95% CI -3.95, -2.07], P<0.001) (Figure 1D, Supplementary Table S6). Fasting plasma insulin decreased the most from baseline at 26 weeks (effect size -3.77 ± 0.91 mIU/L [95% CI -5.57, -1.97], P<0.001), and remained below baseline at 104 weeks (effect size -2.36 ± 0.97 mIU/L [95% CI -4.28, -0.43], P=0.017) (Supplementary Table S6).

DJBL group

Over 50 weeks, there was a significant effect of weeks on *changes* in HbA1c [F(3, 94.37) = 46.733, P<0.001] and fasting plasma glucose [F(3, 99.51)=12.13, P<0.001], but weeks had no significant effect on *changes* in fasting plasma insulin [F(3, 94.93)=0.54, P=0.65] and HOMA-IR [F(3, 98.17) = 1.73, P=0.17] (Figure 1C-E, Supplementary Table S7). In post-hoc analysis, HbA1c decreased the most from baseline at 50 weeks (effect size -16.42 ± 1.67 mol/mmol [95% CI -19.74, -13.11], P<0.001) (Figure 1C, Supplementary Table S8). HOMA-IR decreased the most from baseline at 26 weeks (effect size -1.70 ± 0.73 [95% CI -3.15, -0.24], P=0.023) (Figure 1E, Supplementary Table S8). Fasting plasma glucose decreased most from baseline at 26 weeks (effect size -2.45 ± 0.44 mmol/L [95% CI -3.33, -1.57], P<0.001), and remained below baseline at 50 weeks (-1.99 ± 0.46 mmol/L [95% CI -2.90, -1.08], P<0.001) (Figure 1D, Supplementary Table S8).

DJBL vs. SMM groups

Over 50 weeks, there was no significant effect of group*weeks interaction for *changes* in: HbA1c [F(4, 229.79)=0.99, P = 0.41], HOMA-IR [F(4, 215.68) = 1.054, P=0.38], fasting plasma glucose [F(4, 220.89)=1.831, P=0.12] and fasting plasma insulin [F(4, 216.75)=1.43, P=0.22] (Supplementary Table S9). There was a significant effect of weeks on HbA1c [F(4, 229.79)=44.967, P<0.001], HOMA-IR [F(4, 229.17)=5.452, P<0.001] and fasting plasma glucose [F(4, 234.82)=19.42, P<0.001], but not on fasting serum insulin [F(4, 231.71)=2.41, P=0.05] (Table S9). There was no significant effect of group on HbA1c [F(1, 69.49)=1.026, P=0.31], HOMA-IR [F(1, 66.94)=0.450, P=0.50] or fasting serum insulin [F(1, 66.39)=2.34, P=0.13], but a significant group effect on fasting plasma glucose [F(1, 66.44)=7.737, P=0.007] (Supplementary Table S9). In post-hoc analysis, there were no significant group difference in *changes* in HbA1c, HOMA-IR, fasting plasma glucose or fasting serum insulin from baseline (Figure 1C-E, Supplementary Table S10).

3.2.2. Longitudinal changes in fasting triglycerides

SMM group

There was a significant effect of weeks on *changes* in serum triglycerides [F(4, 95.34)=2.49, P=0.048] (Figure 1F, Supplementary Table S5). In post-hoc analysis, serum triglycerides decreased the most from baseline at 2 weeks (-0.452 ± 0.175 mol/mmol, P=0.011) (Figure 1F, Supplementary Table S6).

DJBL group

There was a non-significant main effect of visit on *changes* in serum triglycerides [F(3, 78.25)=1.651, P=0.19] (Figure 1F, Supplementary Table S7). In post-hoc analysis, serum triglycerides decreased from baseline at 2 weeks (-0.734 ± 0.331 mol/mmol, P=0.030) (Figure 1F, Supplementary Table S8).

DJBL vs. SMM groups

There was no significant effect of group*visit interaction for *changes* in serum triglycerides [F(4, 173.92)=0.53, P=0.71] (Supplementary Table S11). There was a significant effect of visit on *changes* in serum triglycerides [F(4, 173.92)=2.79, P=0.028] (Supplementary Table S11). There was no significant effect of group on *changes* in serum triglycerides [F(1, 57.88)=0.96, P=0.33] (Supplementary Table S11). In post-hoc analysis,

there was no significant between group differences in *changes* in serum triglycerides (Figure 1F, Supplementary Table S12).

3.2.2. Longitudinal changes in fasting appetite ratings

SMM group

There was no significant effect of weeks on *changes* in fasting appetite ratings [F(4, 96.04)=1.022, P=0.40] (Figure 1H, Supplementary Table S5). In post-hoc analysis, there were no significant *changes* in appetite ratings (Figure 1H, Supplementary Table S6).

DJBL group

There was a significant effect of weeks on *changes* in fasted appetite ratings [F(3, 88.79)=4.156, P=0.008] (Figure 1H, Supplementary Table S7). In post-hoc analysis, appetite ratings decreased from baseline at 2 weeks (effect size -10.23 ± 3.89 mm [95% CI -17.96, -2.49], P=0.010) (Figure 1H, Supplementary Table S8,).

DJBL vs. SMM groups

There was no significant effect of group*visit interaction for *changes* in appetite ratings [F(4, 207.02)=0.40, P=0.81] (Supplementary Table S11). There was a significant effect of weeks on *changes* in appetite ratings [F(4, 220.04)=2.90, P=0.02] (Supplementary Table S11). There was no significant effect of group on *changes* in appetite ratings [F(1, 63.46)=0.18, P=0.67] (Figure 1H, Supplementary Table S11). In post-hoc analysis, there was no significant between group differences in change in appetite ratings (Figure 1H, Supplementary Table S12).

3.3.4. Correlations with fasting appetite ratings

SMM group

Over 104 weeks, *absolute* fasting plasma LEAP2 did not correlate with *absolute* fasted appetite ratings (Table S13; Figure 2G), even when including *absolute* glucose as a covariate (Table S13). *Changes* in fasting plasma LEAP2 also did not correlate with *changes* in fasted appetite ratings (Table S13; Figure 2H), and when

including *changes* in glucose as a covariate (Table S13).

DJBL group

Over 50 weeks, *absolute* fasting plasma LEAP2 did not correlate with *absolute* fasted appetite ratings (Figure 3G, Supplementary Table S15), even when including *absolute* fasting plasma glucose as a covariate (Supplementary Table S15). *Changes* in fasting plasma LEAP2 did not correlate with *changes* in fasted appetite ratings (Figure 3H, Supplementary Table S15), even when including *changes* in fasting plasma glucose as a covariate (Supplementary Table S15).

DJBL vs. SMM groups

There was a more negative correlation in DJBL vs. SMM for correlation of *absolute* fasting plasma LEAP2 with *absolute* fasted appetite ratings ($P=0.042$, Supplementary Table S18), with a trend for group effect when including *absolute* fasting plasma glucose as a covariate ($P=0.046$, Supplementary Table S18). There was no significant between-group difference in correlation of *changes* in fasting plasma LEAP2 with *changes* in fasted appetite ratings, even when including *changes* in fasting plasma glucose as a covariate ($P=0.85-0.93$, Supplementary Table S19).

3.3.5. Correlations with fasting hunger ratings

SMM group

Absolute fasting plasma LEAP2 did not correlate with *absolute* fasted hunger ratings (Supplementary Figure S3G, Table S18). *Changes* in fasting plasma LEAP2 also did not correlate with *changes* in fasted hunger ratings (Supplementary Figure S3H, Table S19).

DJBL group

Absolute fasting plasma LEAP2 did not correlate with *absolute* fasted hunger ratings (Supplementary Figure S4G, Table S18). *Changes* in fasting plasma LEAP2 also did not correlate with *changes* in fasted hunger ratings (Supplementary Figure S4H, Table S19).

DJBL vs. SMM groups

There was a more negative correlation in DJBL vs. SMM for correlation of *absolute* fasting plasma LEAP2 with *absolute* fasted hunger ratings (P=0.046, Supplementary Table S18). There were no significant between group differences in correlations of *changes* in hunger with *changes* in plasma LEAP2 (P=0.91, Supplementary Table S19).

3.3.6. Correlation analysis of fasting plasma LEAP2 with outcome variables after DJBL explant

Correlations with weight

Changes in fasting plasma LEAP2 did not correlate with *changes* in weight between 50 and 104 weeks after DJBL explant (Supplementary Figure S6A, Table S20).

Correlations with glucose metabolism markers

Changes in fasting plasma LEAP2 did not correlate with *changes* in: HbA1c, HOMA-IR, fasting plasma glucose and serum insulin between 50 and 104 weeks after DJBL explant (Supplementary Figure S6B-E, Table S20).

Correlations with triglycerides

Changes in fasting plasma LEAP2 did not correlate with *changes* in fasting serum triglycerides between 50 and 104 weeks after DJBL explant (Supplementary Figure S6F, Table S20).

Correlations with appetite and hunger ratings

Changes in fasting plasma LEAP2 did not correlate with *changes* in fasting appetite ratings or fasting hunger ratings between 50 and 104 weeks after DJBL explant (Supplementary Figure S6G,H, Table S20).

3.4.1. Longitudinal analysis of weight in post-prandial sub-group

DJBL vs. SMM groups

There was a significant group*weeks interaction for weight [F(3, 90.95)=4.51, P=0.005] (Supplementary Table

S21). In post-hoc analysis, weight loss was significantly greater in DJBL vs. SMM at week 26 (effect size $-3.53 \pm 1.01\%$ [95% CI $-5.53, -1.52$], $P=0.001$) and week 50 (effect size $-3.41 \pm 1.16\%$ [95% CI $-5.70, -1.11$], $P=0.004$) (Figure 4A, Supplementary Table S22).

3.4.5. Longitudinal analysis of post-prandial appetite and fullness ratings

SMM group

There was no significant effect of weeks on post-prandial appetite $iAUC_{0-120min}$ [$F(3, 29.6)=0.61$, $P=0.61$] or post-prandial fullness $iAUC_{0-120min}$ [$F(3, 30.06)=1.65$, $P=0.20$] (Supplementary Table S28). In post-hoc analysis, there were no significant differences in appetite $iAUC_{0-120min}$ between weeks (Supplementary Figure S7A, Table S29). The largest decrease in post-prandial fullness $iAUC_{0-120min}$ was at week 50 (-2064.26 ± 957.42 mm.min, $P=0.039$) (Supplementary Figure S7B, Table S29).

DJBL group

There was no significant effect of weeks on post-prandial appetite $iAUC_{0-120min}$ [$F(3, 47.34)=1.421$, $P=0.25$] but a significant effect of weeks on post-prandial fullness $iAUC_{0-120min}$ [$F(3, 42.46)=3.63$, $P=0.020$] (Supplementary Figure S7A,B, Table S28). In post-hoc analysis, there were no significant differences in appetite $iAUC_{0-120min}$ between visits (Supplementary Figure S7A, Table S29). Post-prandial fullness $iAUC_{0-120min}$ tended to be lower at 26 vs -2 weeks (-1277.12 ± 590.72 mm.min, $P=0.036$) (Supplementary Figure S7B, Table S29).

DJBL vs. SMM groups

There was no significant group*weeks interaction for post-prandial appetite $iAUC_{0-120min}$ [$F(3, 74.96)=1.12$, $P=0.35$], but a significant interaction for post-prandial fullness $iAUC_{0-120min}$ [$F(3, 72.52)=3.97$, $P=0.011$] (Supplementary Table S28). There was no significant effect of visit on post-prandial appetite $iAUC_{0-120min}$ [$F(3, 74.96)=0.60$, $P=0.61$] or effect of group on post-prandial appetite $iAUC_{0-120min}$ [$F(1, 32.63)=0.05$, $P=0.83$] (Supplementary Table S28). However, in post-hoc analysis, there were no group differences in post-prandial appetite $iAUC_{0-120min}$ or post-prandial fullness $iAUC_{0-120min}$ at any visit (Supplementary Figure S7A,B, Table S29).

3.4.6 Correlation with post-prandial appetite iAUC

SMM group

Absolute plasma LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} did not correlate with *absolute* appetite iAUC_{0-120min} (Supplementary Table S30, Figure S7C), even when including *absolute* plasma glucose iAUC_{0-120min} as a covariate (Supplementary Table S30, Figure S7C). *Changes* in plasma LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} did not correlate with *changes* in appetite iAUC_{0-120min} (Supplementary Table S30, Figure S7D), even when including *changes* in plasma glucose iAUC_{0-120min} as a covariate (Supplementary Table S30).

DJBL group

Absolute plasma LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} did not correlate with *absolute* appetite iAUC_{0-120min} (Supplementary Table S30, Figure S7E), even when including *absolute* plasma glucose iAUC_{0-120min} as a covariate (Supplementary Table S30). *Changes* in plasma LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} did not correlate with *changes* in appetite iAUC_{0-120min} (Supplementary Table S30, Figure S7F), even when including *changes* in plasma glucose iAUC_{0-120min} as a covariate (Supplementary Table S30).

DJBL vs. SMM groups

There were no significant between group differences in correlation of *absolute* or *changes* in LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} correlation with *absolute* and *changes* in appetite iAUC_{0-120min} (P=0.79-0.96), even when including *absolute* and *changes* in plasma glucose iAUC_{0-120min} (P=0.25-0.60) (Supplementary Table S30).

3.4.6 Correlations with post-prandial fullness iAUC

SMM group

Absolute plasma LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} did not correlate with *absolute* fullness iAUC_{0-120min} (Supplementary Table S30). *Changes* in plasma LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} did not correlate with *changes* in fullness iAUC_{0-120min} (Supplementary Table S30).

DJBL group

Absolute plasma LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} did not correlate with *absolute* fullness iAUC_{0-120min} (Supplementary Table S30). *Changes* in plasma LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} did not correlate with *changes* in fullness iAUC_{0-120min} (Supplementary Table S30).

DJBL vs. SMM groups

There were no significant between group differences in correlations of *absolute* and *changes* in plasma LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} with *absolute* and *changes* in fullness iAUC_{0-120min} (P=0.24-0.75) (Supplementary Table S30).

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Figure S1. Study design: outline of randomised controlled trial.

Participants at the screening visit, were randomised into duodenal-jejunal bypass liner (DJBL) insertion or standard medical management (SMM) alone and further divided into a mechanistic taste subgroup (blue box). Visits at -2, 2, 26 weeks are similar, where data used for analysis: fasting bloods (both sub-groups) and post-prandial bloods (taste sub-group only); anthropological measurements (weight, height, body fat percentage, fasting bloods) and appetite ratings (visits at -2, 2, 26, 50, 104 weeks); sweet detection task (-2, 2, 26 weeks) and fixed meal consumption (-2, 2, 26, 50 weeks) in taste sub-group only (blue box). Liquid diet of 1300 kcal (females) or 1500 kcal (males) was taken by all participants across both groups from -1 to 2 weeks. At 52 weeks, the DJBL device was removed, with 104 weeks being the 1-year follow-up after the DJBL implant was removed. Adapted from (Glaysher et al. 2017).

Figure S2. Longitudinal analysis of absolute fasting plasma LEAP2 across visits.

Absolute fasting plasma LEAP2 across time for participants undergoing standard medical management alone (SMM, blue dashed line) and duodenal-jejunal bypass liner (DJBL, red solid line) groups. Black bar indicates duration of DJBL being in situ (0-52 weeks). N indicates number of participants at each time point. Grey bar indicates duration of liquid diet (-1 to 2 weeks). Statistical results below graph indicates linear mixed model analysis including group (SMM, DJBL) and sweet taste detection task (present for taste sub-group at weeks -2, 2 and 26 only) as between participant factors, and weeks (-2, 2, 26, 50, 104) as within participant fixed factor, to examine effects of interventions on fasting plasma LEAP2 over time. DJBL vs. SMM: * P<0.05, ** P<0.01, *** P<0.005, **** P<0.001; DJBL vs. baseline week -2: # P<0.05, ## P<0.01, ### P<0.005, #### P<0.001; SMM vs. baseline week -2: \$ P<0.05, \$\$ P<0.01, \$\$\$ P<0.005, \$\$\$\$ P<0.001. All data given as mean \pm SEM. Abbreviations: kcal, kilocalorie.

Figure S3. Correlations of absolute and change in fasting plasma LEAP2 with absolute and change in HbA1c, fasting insulin, triglycerides and hunger ratings across visits in SMM group.

Correlations of absolute fasting plasma LEAP2 with absolute fasting (A) HbA1c, (C) serum insulin, (E) serum triglycerides, (G) hunger VAS ratings across visits -2, 2, 26, 50 and 104 weeks; and correlations of change in fasting plasma LEAP2 with change in fasting (B) HbA1c, (D) serum insulin, (F) serum triglycerides and (H) hunger VAS ratings between weeks 2, 26, 50 and 104 vs. -2 weeks. Statistical analysis used linear mixed model analysis with weeks (-2, 2, 26, 50, 104) as within participant fixed factor, to examine relationships between absolute and changes in fasting plasma LEAP2 over time, and metabolic parameters and hunger ratings (using values corrected for sweet taste detection task for fasting serum insulin and plasma LEAP2 in taste sub-group at weeks -2, 2 and 26 only). Results given as pseudo r^2 and beta parameters. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$, **** $P < 0.0001$, $n = 22-30$. Abbreviations: SMM, standard medical management, VAS, visual analogue scale.

A Fasting LEAP2 vs. HbA1c - DJBL

Figure S4. Correlations of absolute and change in fasting plasma LEAP2 with absolute and change in HbA1c, fasting insulin, triglycerides and hunger ratings across visits in DJBL group.

Correlations of absolute fasting plasma LEAP2 with absolute fasting (A) HbA1c, (C) serum insulin, (E) serum triglycerides, (G) hunger VAS ratings across visits -2, 2, 26, 50 and 104 weeks; and correlations of change in fasting plasma LEAP2 with change in fasting (B) HbA1c, (D) serum insulin, (F) serum triglycerides and (H) hunger VAS ratings between weeks 2, 26, 50 and 104 vs. -2 weeks. Statistical analysis used linear mixed model analysis with weeks (-2, 2, 26, 50 and 104) as within participant fixed factor, to examine relationships between absolute and changes in fasting plasma LEAP2 over time, and metabolic parameters and hunger ratings (using values corrected for sweet taste detection task for fasting serum insulin and plasma LEAP2 in taste sub-group at weeks -2, 2 and 26 only). Results given as pseudo r^2 and beta parameters. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$, **** $P < 0.0001$, $n = 22-30$. Abbreviations: DJBL, duodenal-jejunal bypass liner; VAS, visual analogue scale.

Figure S5. Correlations of absolute fasting plasma LEAP2 with absolute fasting HOMA-IR and triglycerides in SMM and DJBL groups.

Correlations of absolute fasting plasma LEAP2 with (A,B) absolute fasting HOMA-IR and (C,D) absolute fasting serum triglycerides in (A,C) SMM and (B,D) SMM groups, across visits -2, 2, 26 and 50 weeks. Statistical analysis used linear mixed model analysis with weeks (-2, 2, 26 and 50) as within participant fixed factor, to examine relationships between fasting plasma LEAP2 and metabolic parameters over time using values corrected for sweet taste detection task for fasting serum insulin and plasma LEAP2 in taste sub-group at weeks -2, 2 and 26 only). Results given as pseudo r^2 and beta parameters. * $P<0.05$, ** $P<0.01$, *** $P<0.001$, **** $P<0.0001$, $n=22-30$. Abbreviations: DJBL, duodenal-jejunal bypass liner; HOMA-IR, homeostatic model assessment for insulin resistance; SMM, standard medical management.

Figure S6. Correlations of change in fasting plasma LEAP2 with change in weight, HbA1c, fasting glucose, insulin, HOMA-IR, triglycerides, appetite and hunger ratings after DJBL explant.

Correlations of change in fasting plasma LEAP2 with change in (A) weight, (B) HbA1c, fasting (C) plasma glucose, (D) serum insulin, (E) HOMA-IR, (F) serum triglycerides, (G) appetite and (H) hunger VAS ratings between weeks 50 and 100 (Δ 50-100weeks) from the period of DJBL explant (at 52 weeks) using Pearson's (r_p , linear regression line) correlation coefficients. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.005$, **** $P < 0.001$, $n = 10-21$. Abbreviations: DJBL, duodenal-jejunal bypass liner; HOMA-IR, homeostatic model assessment for insulin resistance; kg, kilogram; VAS, visual analogue scale.

C Appetite iAUC_{0-120min} vs. LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} - SMM

D Δ Appetite iAUC_{0-120min} vs. Δ LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} - SMM

E Appetite iAUC_{0-120min} vs. LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} - DJBL

F Δ Appetite iAUC_{0-120min} vs. Δ LEAP2 iAUC_{0-120min} - DJBL

Figure S7. Longitudinal analysis of post-prandial appetite and fullness ratings across visits and correlations with post-prandial plasma LEAP2.

(A,B) Post-prandial (A) appetite iAUC and (B) fullness VAS iAUC ratings from t=0 min to t=120 min after consumption of a fixed 600 kcal test meal (49% carbohydrate, 35% fat, 16% protein) for participants undergoing standard medical management alone (SMM, blue dashed line) or with additional duodenal-jejunal bypass liner insertion (DJBL, red solid line) groups. Black bar indicates duration of DJBL being in situ (0-52 weeks). N indicates number of participants at each time point. Grey bar indicates duration of liquid diet (-1 to 2 weeks). Statistical analysis used linear mixed model analysis including group (SMM, DJBL) as between participant factor, and weeks (-2, 2, 26 and 50) as within participant fixed factor, to examine effects of interventions on dependent variables over time. DJBL vs. SMM: nil significant; DJBL vs. baseline week -2: nil significant; SMM vs. baseline week -2: $\$ P < 0.05$. All data given as mean \pm SEM.

(C-F) Correlations of (C,E) *absolute* post-prandial plasma LEAP2 iAUC with *absolute* post-prandial appetite VAS iAUC ratings from t=0 min to t=120 min after consumption of a fixed 600kcal test meal (49% carbohydrate, 35% fat, 16% protein) in the taste sub-group across visits -2, 2, 26 and 50 weeks; and (D,F) *change* in post-prandial plasma LEAP2 iAUC from t=0 min to t=120 min with *change* in post-prandial appetite iAUC VAS ratings between weeks 2, 26 and 50 vs. -2 weeks, in (C,D) SMM group and (E,F) DJBL group. Statistical analysis used linear mixed model analysis with weeks (-2, 2, 26 and 50) as within participant fixed factor, to examine relationships between post-prandial plasma LEAP2 and appetite over time. Results reported as pseudo r^2 and beta parameters, n=9-13.

Abbreviations: DJBL, duodenal-jejunal bypass liner; iAUC, incremental area under the curve; kcal, kilocalorie SMM, standard medical management; VAS, visual analogue scale.

Figure S8. Distribution of medication use among both SMM and DJBL groups across visits.

Bar graphs describing prevalence of medication use in (A) SMM and (B) DJBL groups at -2, 2, 26, 50 and 104 weeks as % of participants. Abbreviations: SU, sulphonylureas; DPP4i, dipeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors; SGLT2i, sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 inhibitors; TZD, thiazolidinediones; GLP1RA, glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists; PPI, proton pump inhibitors; SMM, standard medical management; DJBL, duodenal-jejunal bypass liner.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES

Please see accompanying Supplementary Tables Excel file.

SUPPLEMENTARY REFERENCES

- Bhargava R, Luur S, Rodriguez Flores M, Emini M, Prechtl CG & Goldstone AP (2023). Post-prandial increases in liver-gut hormone LEAP2 correlate with attenuated eating behaviour in adults without obesity. *J Endocr Soc*, 7: bvad061.
- Glaysheer MA, Mohanaruban A, Prechtl CG, Goldstone AP, Miras AD, Lord J, Chhina N, Falaschetti E, Johnson NA, Al-Najim W, Smith C, Li JV, Patel M, Ahmed AR, Moore M, Poulter N, Bloom S, Darzi A, Le Roux C, Byrne JP & Teare JP (2017). A randomised controlled trial of a duodenal-jejunal bypass sleeve device (EndoBarrier) compared with standard medical therapy for the management of obese subjects with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *BMJ Open*, 7: e018598.
- Mani BK, Puzziferri N, He Z, Rodriguez JA, Osborne-Lawrence S, Metzger NP, Chhina N, Gaylinn B, Thorner MO, Thomas EL, Bell JD, Williams KW, Goldstone AP & Zigman JM (2019). LEAP2 changes with body mass and food intake in humans and mice. *J Clin Invest*, 129: 3909-3923.
- Matthews DR, Hosker JP, Rudenski AS, Naylor BA, Treacher DF & Turner RC (1985). Homeostasis model assessment: insulin resistance and beta-cell function from fasting plasma glucose and insulin concentrations in man. *Diabetologia*, 28: 412-419.
- Ruban A, Glaysheer MA, Miras AD, Goldstone AP, Prechtl CG, Johnson N, Li J, Aldhwayan M, Aldubaikhi G, Glover B, Lord J, Onyimadu O, Falaschetti E, Klimowska-Nassar N, Ashrafian H, Byrne J & Teare JP (2020). A duodenal sleeve bypass device added to intensive medical therapy for obesity with type 2 diabetes: a RCT. *Efficacy and Mechanism Evaluation*, doi:10.3310/eme07060.